

Complexometric Determination of Palladium(II) using Thiocarbohydrazide as a Masking Reagent

B. NARAYANA*, M. R. GAJENDRAGAD and K. SUBRAHMANYA BHAT

Department of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 24 July 1996, revised 28 January 1997, accepted 11 April 1997

A selective complexometric method for the determination of palladium(II) in presence of various metal ions is more useful because palladium is associated with gold, platinum, silver or nickel ores. The direct complexometric method for palladium determination have mostly dealt with its determination in pure solution or in the presence of platinum group metals which do not form complexes with EDTA. Many other reagents have been used for the complexometric determination of palladium, as discussed earlier¹, but some of the reagents need stringent conditions for preparation and some require tedious and time-consuming masking procedures to avoid interferences.

The present paper discusses thiocarbohydrazide as a masking agent, which provides rapid masking at room temperature, enabling an EDTA titration to give an indirect determination of palladium.

Results and Discussion

The fact that thiocarbohydrazide (TCH) displaces EDTA quantitatively from Pd-EDTA complex indicates that Pd-TCH complex is more stable than Pd-EDTA complex. The Pd-TCH complex is water-soluble. Thus the absence of any precipitate in the reaction mixture favours sharp end-points. Larger excess of the reagent over 1 : 3 molar ratio of metal-to-ligand has no adverse effects on the accuracy of the determination. The effect of diverse metal ions, rare earth ions and anions on the quantitative determination of Pd^{II} is studied with 5.39 mg of Pd^{II} in an aliquot. Hg^{II}, Tl^{III}, Sn^{IV} and Zr^{IV} were found to interfere. The interference can be avoided by using appropriate secondary masking agents. The following ions did not interfere within the ranges studied (< 0.37% error): Ni^{II}, Fe^{III} (30 mg); Ce^{III}, Al^{III}, La^{III}, Bi^{III}, Ti^{IV}, V^{IV} (20 mg); Zn^{II} (50 mg); Cd^{II} (80 mg); Mn^{II} (5 mg); Cr^{III} (10 mg).

The determination of Pd^{II} from palladium(II) chloride solution (2.7–27 mg) shows that accurate and reproducible results are obtainable with permissible relative errors $\leq 0.05\%$ and standard deviations ≤ 0.05 mg. The proposed method works well in the range 2.7–27 mg of Pd^{II} and is simple and accurate. It does not need heating or cooling before or during titration and also does not need solvent extraction. The lack of effect of diverse metal ions on the accuracy and precision of the method reveals that it may be suitable for the determination of palladium in its alloys.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. A stock solution of palladium was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride (1 g) in excess of KCl followed by dilution to 1 dm³ and standardised². Lead nitrate solution (0.01 M) was standardised². Solutions of EDTA (0.02 M), xylenol orange (0.05%) and thiocarbohydrazide (0.5%) containing a few drops of perchloric acid and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer were prepared in the usual way.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution containing 2–27 mg of palladium, an excess of 0.02 M EDTA solution was added and diluted to 70–80 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0–6.0 by adding sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. The excess EDTA was then back-titrated against the standard lead nitrate solution to the sharp colour change of the xylenol orange indicator. To this solution was added an excess of thiocarbohydrazide solution in water (one-fold excess over the molar ratio of 1 : 2 (metal : ligand)). The contents were mixed well and allowed to stand for 3–5 min. The liberated EDTA was titrated against the lead nitrate solution. The second titre value corresponded to the amount of Pd^{II} present in the aliquot.

Analysis of Pd^{II} complexes : Palladium(II) complexes with some mercapto ligands were prepared by the conventional method and their purity was checked by elemental analysis. Each complex (0.2–0.4 g) was decomposed by evaporation nearly to dryness with aqua regia. The residue was then cooled, dissolved in dilute KCl solution and made up to 100 ml with distilled water. Aliquots (10 ml) were used for titration by the proposed procedure. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF PALLADIUM COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Pd Present %	Pd Found %
Pd(CH ₅ N ₃ S) ₂ Cl ₂ ^a	29.61	29.52
Pd(C ₉ H ₇ N ₄ OS) ₂ ^b	19.54	19.01
Pd(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS) ₂ ^c	18.45	18.31
Pd(C ₄ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂) ₂ ^d	31.62	31.75

*Palladium complex of : ^athiosemicarbazide, ^b4-amino-3-mercapto-6-phenyl-1,2,4-triazin-(4H)-5-one, ^c4-amino-5-mercapto-3-(*o*-tolylloxymethyl)-1,2,4-triazole, ^ddimethylglyoxime.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Pd^{II} IN ARTIFICIAL MIXTURE OF SALTS CONTAINING ALLOY COMPOSITIONS

Mixture* (250 ml)	Composition %	Pd found** %	Relative std. dev. %	Relative error %
PdCl ₂ + NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (0.2541 + 0.4663)g	61 + 39	60.8	0.2	-0.3
PdCl ₂ + CoCO ₃ (0.2708 + 0.1766)g	65 + 35	64.7	0.1	-0.5
PdCl ₂ + AuCl ₃ (0.2083 + 0.1925)g	50 + 50	49.9	0.2	-0.2

*250 ml. **Average of four determinations. "Flouride is used to mask Au^{III}.

Analysis of Pd^{II} in artificial mixture of salts : Mixtures of NiSO₄·7H₂O, CoCO₃ or AuCl₃ with PdCl₂ were prepared and dissolved in minimum amount of dilute HCl and made upto 50 ml. Aliquots (10 ml) were used for titration and analysed using the proposed method (Table 2).

References

1. B. NARAYANA and M. R. GAJENDRAGAD, *Microchem. J.*, 1987, **36**, 364; *Curr. Sci.*, 1987, **56**, 1279; B. M. RAO and B. NARAYANA, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)*, 1993, **83**, 431; B. M. RAO, B. NARAYANA and B. MATHEW, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1995, **118**, 63; B. MATHEW, B. NARAYANA, B. M. RAO and C. H. R. NAMBIAR, 1996, **124**, 167.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed., Longmans, London, 1978.